

HALAL CULINARY TOURISM MARKETING MANAGEMENT IN MEDAN CITY

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ABSTRACT

Objective: The present study investigates the correlation that exists between the marketing efforts of Medan's tourism sector and the development of halal culinary tourism.

Method: The research employs structural equation modeling (SEM) to examine a multitude of variables, including marketing, location, cost, and restaurant amenities.

Result and Discussion: The findings of the study reveal that halal culinary tourism is impacted by location, amenities, price, and promotion to the tune of 25.9%. While tourism promotion accounted for 13.7% of halal culinary tourism, the remaining 86.3% was determined by other factors.

Implications for Research: The Islamic promotional variable did not result in a discernible expansion of halal culinary tourism, according to the study's findings. Local and provincial governments, according to the study, must provide support for the efficient administration of culinary tourism promotion.

Keywords: Price; Promotions; Location; Facilities; Tourism Marketing; Halal Culinary Tours

GESTÃO DE MARKETING DE TURISMO CULINÁRIO HALAL NA CIDADE DE MEDAN

RESUMO

Objetivo: O presente estudo investiga a correlação que existe entre os esforços de marketing do setor turístico de Medan e o desenvolvimento do turismo culinário halal.

Método: A pesquisa emprega modelagem de equações estruturais (SEM) para examinar uma infinidade de variáveis, incluindo marketing, localização, custo e comodidades do restaurante.

Resultado e Discussão: As conclusões do estudo revelam que o turismo culinário halal é impactado pela localização, comodidades, preço e promoção em 25,9%. Enquanto a promoção turística representou 13,7% do turismo culinário halal, os restantes 86,3% foram determinados por outros factores.

Implicações para a investigação: A variável promocional islâmica não resultou numa expansão discernível do turismo culinário halal, de acordo com as conclusões do estudo. Os governos locais e provinciais, segundo o estudo, devem apoiar a administração eficiente da promoção do turismo gastronómico.

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Palavras-chave: Preço; Promoções; Localização; Instalações; Marketing Turístico; Passeios Culinários Halal

GESTIÓN DEL MARKETING TURÍSTICO CULINARIO HALAL EN LA CIUDAD DE MEDAN

RESUMEN

Objetivo: El presente estudio investiga la correlación que existe entre los esfuerzos de marketing del sector turístico de Medan y el desarrollo del turismo culinario halal.

Método: La investigación emplea modelos de ecuaciones estructurales (SEM) para examinar una multitud de variables, incluido el marketing, la ubicación, el costo y los servicios del restaurante.

Resultado y discusión: Los hallazgos del estudio revelan que el turismo culinario halal se ve afectado por la ubicación, las comodidades, el precio y la promoción en un 25,9%. Mientras que la promoción turística representó el 13,7% del turismo gastronómico halal, el 86,3% restante estuvo determinado por otros factores.

Implicaciones para la investigación: La variable promocional islámica no resultó en una expansión perceptible del turismo culinario halal, según los hallazgos del estudio. Los gobiernos locales y provinciales, según el estudio, deben brindar apoyo para la gestión eficiente de la promoción del turismo gastronómico.

Palabras clave: Precio; Promociones; Ubicación; Instalaciones; Comercialización Turística; Tours Culinarios Halal

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1 INTRODUCTION

Tourism is a growing sector that boosts the global economy due to its GDP contribution. Tourism is also one of the 11 largest sectors that can effectively employ people, boost economic growth, and improve their well-being (Chandra and al, 2023). In the National Medium-term Development Plan (2015–2019), Infrastructure, Maritime, Energy, Food, and Tourism are the five focal points for the next five years. Tourism plays a strategic role in national development. Tourism is one of these five sectors, and the Ministry of Tourism has identified it as a sector of excellence to help the Indonesian economy by designing the Long-Term Development Plan (2005–2025) to meet the needs of local and domestic tourists and boost regional income (Perda Sumut, 2018). Optimization of the tourism sector in Medan is one way to increase Regional Real Income. Tourism is important to a city's progress because it attracts domestic and foreign tourists who visit and invest. Medan-centered tourism makes North Sumatra a tourism hotspot. Due to its strategic location, Medan's tourism sector is growing rapidly, which boosts foreign exchange (Hasibuan and al, 2023). Culinary tourism in Medan City should leverage the city's rich cultural, customs, social, and political wealth to attract tourists.

The number of tourists visiting North Sumatra fluctuated greatly in 2020, due to the COVID-19 pandemic, tourists can't visit its attractions. However (Pratomo, et al, 2019) reported

that Nusantara tourists visiting Samosir increased by 41.158 in 2018 or 92.97% from 2017. About 37 famous tourist attractions in Samosir contribute to the increase in tourists. Therefore, Lake Toba Area tourism should focus on nusantara tourists' basic needs, such as halal cuisine, which is expected to draw tourists back to Samosir. Halal culinary tourism is a new tourism trend with potential. Halal culinary tours meet Muslim tourists' basic needs with Islamic rules, such as providing halal food and beverages, places of worship, and other facilities for the people. The law and secret are Allah's plans for His people's sin in this world and the next.

Based on the aforementioned data, it is evident that Revenue generated within a specific geographic area share of restaurant tax revenue experienced a notable decline in 2019–2021 due to the Covid-19 pandemic, after having surged in 2018. Additionally, upon conducting the observations, it was determined that the lack of public awareness regarding the halal tour concept continues to exert control over halal tourism. Halal tourism encompasses the provision of amenities that are conducive to the needs and preferences of Muslims, including lodging, dining establishments, halal cuisine, suitable places of worship, and additional amenities.

Halal culinary tourism is appealing to tourists due to its promotional offerings of affordable and cost-effective halal food. Aside from the cost, tourists also consider the proximity of the culinary establishment to their place of residence, as well as the amenities provided by the seller to ensure the adherence to halal culinary standards. Halal culinary tourism has the potential to attract tourists if there is effective and targeted marketing. If this goal can be accomplished, it is anticipated to enhance the tourist attraction and subsequently boost the local revenue of the region.

The novelty in this research lies in the selection of the research location, which was determined based on the clusterization of sub-districts in Medan and the analysis of the highest number of culinary visitors in Medan City. For instance, the study focused on the popular culinary destination, Durian Ukok, located in Medan Sub-district. The Bika Ambon Zulaika culinary establishment is located in the Medan Petisah District. The Nasi Soto Sinar Pagi culinary establishment can be found in the Medan Barat District. Pagaruyung culinary is situated in the Medan Petisah District. Sate Memeng culinary is located in the Medan Timur District. Rujak Kolam Takanan Juo culinary can be found in the Medan Kota District. Lontong Kak Lin culinary is situated in the Medan Polonia District. Wajir Seafood culinary is located in the Medan Maimun District. Amaliun Food Court culinary can be found in the Medan Area District. Lastly, Mie Aceh Titi Bobrok culinary is situated in the Medan Sunggal District.

Given the aforementioned issues, no problems were identified concerning the marketing management of halal culinary tourism, specifically in the city of Medan. Consequently, the researcher endeavored to investigate the marketing management of culinary tourism in Medan by analyzing restaurant amenities, location, promotions, and pricing. The study examines tourism marketing as an intervening variable for halal culinary tourism, which is the dependent variable.

2 METHODOLOGY

This study was conducted on ten renowned culinary establishments in the city of Medan that are both captivating and attract a large number of visitors. These establishments include UcoK Durian, Bika Ambon Zulaikha, Soto rice Sinar Pagi, Kuliner Pagaruyung, Sate Memeng, Rujak Kolam Takana Juo, Lontong Kak Lin, Wajir Seafood, Mie Aceh Titi Bobrok, and Amaliun Food Court. The preliminary research phase will commence in January 2020, followed by the collection of questionnaire data from October to December 2021. This data will be gathered using a mixed methodology that incorporates both quantitative and qualitative approaches, with the aim of addressing the problem at hand.

The research collected qualitative data, which refers to data that is not in the form of numbers or word descriptions used for speech, in addition to quantitative data [7]. The data sources are derived from primary data collected from respondents who complete questionnaires through direct interviews. The interviews are conducted systematically, with a focus on addressing research issues, objectives, and hypotheses.

Sample determination is conducted through convenience sampling, wherein respondents are chosen based on their willingness to complete both male and female questionnaires, as well as their age and occupation, in order to ensure the researcher receives precise and sufficient information (Fatimah, 2019). Based on (Sarwono and al, 2015), the minimum number of samples required for research using Partial Least Squares - Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) analysis is between 30 and 100 samples. The study will collect samples from a total of 260 tourists, who will be evenly distributed among each research location.

The research employed two analytical methods: Descriptive Statistics, which offers a comprehensive overview of the collected data, and Partial Least Squares Analysis - Structural Equation Modeling (SEM), which is a technique used to develop or predict existing theories, facilitated by the use of Smart PLS 3.0 software.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

1. Outer Model Test

Outer Model testing focuses on assessing the accuracy and consistency of a model. The examination of this test will be assessed based on the impacts of Factor Loading, Average Variance Extracted (AVE), Discriminant Validity, and Composite Reliability (Panca W, 2017).

2. Factor Loading

Factor loading is an initial step in assessing the validity of a model, with the requirement that the factor loading must be greater than 0.6 for the indicator to be considered valid. If the data is invalid, it should be eliminated from the model (Husein, 2015). The external analysis of this research model can be observed in Figure 1 below:

Source: Data Analysis, 2021

3. Average Variance Extracted (AVE)

The Average Variance Extracted (AVE) is a metric used in convergence validity testing. It is derived from the concept of convergent validity. In this study, the anticipated average variance extracted (AVE) value is greater than 0.5. When examining the latent variable structure, all constructs have values above 0.5. For a clearer understanding, please refer to Table 4 for the AVE results.

Table 1. AVE Output Influence Price, Promotion and Location on Culinary Tourism Marketing

Variable	Varians Diekstrak (AVE)
X1 Price	0,51
X2 Promotion	0,55
X3 Location	0,54
X4 Fasility	0,52
Z Tourism Marketing	0,52
Y Halal Culinary Tourism	0,51

Source: Data Analysis, 2021

Given the absence of any issues regarding convergent validity, the subsequent step is to examine a potential problem concerning discriminant validity.

4. Discriminant Validity

Cross Loading tables assess discriminant validity. This table compares the correlation between indicators and latent variables within and outside the block to test the indicator's discriminant validity. For enhanced lucidity, please refer to Table 5 below.

Table 2. Discriminant Validity

	X1	X2	X3	X4	Y	Z
X1.1	0,547	0,097	0,106	-0,001	0,170	0,070
X1.2	0,723	0,071	0,171	0,116	0,170	0,288
X1.3	0,798	0,042	0,199	0,132	0,205	0,277
X1.4	0,813	0,053	0,205	0,132	0,173	0,271
X1.5	0,742	0,107	0,229	0,106	0,135	0,229
X1.6	0,635	0,160	0,168	0,142	0,121	0,210
X2.1	0,188	0,536	0,165	0,126	0,172	0,116
X2.2	0,091	0,764	0,167	0,096	0,217	0,132
X2.3	0,039	0,787	0,112	0,050	0,280	0,069
X2.4	0,097	0,805	0,114	0,022	0,237	0,124
X2.5	0,039	0,857	0,089	0,037	0,247	0,104
X2.6	0,112	0,795	0,173	0,007	0,243	0,131
X2.7	0,082	0,759	0,076	0,012	0,241	0,109
X2.8	0,039	0,558	0,196	0,072	0,154	0,084
X3.1	0,169	0,252	0,698	0,176	0,172	0,190
X3.10	0,189	0,093	0,705	0,214	0,084	0,290
X3.2	0,187	0,202	0,716	0,197	0,092	0,184
X3.3	0,196	0,183	0,687	0,224	0,181	0,161
X3.4	0,174	0,198	0,671	0,205	0,193	0,202
X3.5	0,156	0,096	0,718	0,193	0,044	0,136
X3.6	0,154	0,091	0,770	0,206	0,011	0,255
X3.7	0,209	0,094	0,800	0,256	0,058	0,328
X3.8	0,206	0,044	0,806	0,341	0,039	0,326
X3.9	0,213	0,108	0,753	0,227	0,086	0,251
X4.1	0,186	0,111	0,281	0,676	0,010	0,252
X4.2	0,169	0,028	0,260	0,724	0,035	0,286
X4.3	0,121	0,091	0,189	0,779	0,085	0,340
X4.4	0,089	0,007	0,226	0,755	0,060	0,271
X4.5	0,080	0,029	0,197	0,704	0,031	0,297
X4.6	0,041	0,018	0,212	0,674	-0,015	0,304
Y.1	0,136	0,195	0,159	0,012	0,653	0,151
Y.2	0,120	0,225	0,095	0,073	0,733	0,142
Y.3	0,131	0,273	0,048	-0,015	0,785	0,146
Y.4	0,181	0,268	0,106	0,051	0,786	0,219

	X1	X2	X3	X4	Y	Z
Y.5	0,102	0,227	0,132	0,014	0,672	0,118
Y.6	0,252	0,136	0,106	0,106	0,684	0,221
Y.7	0,202	0,199	0,012	0,014	0,678	0,165
Z.1	0,125	0,083	0,282	0,295	0,095	0,673
Z.2	0,246	0,071	0,299	0,351	0,188	0,731
Z.3	0,237	0,043	0,254	0,297	0,164	0,767
Z.4	0,252	0,162	0,221	0,292	0,222	0,758
Z.5	0,236	0,160	0,199	0,260	0,207	0,740
Z.6	0,319	0,111	0,181	0,264	0,122	0,649

Source: Data Analysis, 2021

5. Concrete Reliability Test

In order to mitigate any issues pertaining to measurement, the final stage in assessing the external model involves testing the unidimensionality of the model. The threshold value for both indicators is 0.7

Table 3. Composite Reliability

	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability
X1	0,808	0,861
X2	0,878	0,905
X3	0,905	0,921
X4	0,813	0,865
Y	0,839	0,879
Z	0,814	0,866

Source: Data Analysis, 2021

The table above indicates that the entire structure has a composite reliability value exceeding 0.7. Thus, no issue of unidimensionality was detected regarding the impact of price, promotion, and location on the marketing of halal culinary tourism.

6. Inner Model Test

Coefficient of Determination R² (R-Square), the quality of fit on the Partial Least Squares (PLS) model can be determined by the Q² value. The value Q² is equivalent to the determination coefficient (R-Square) in regression analysis.

Table 4. R Square Model

	R Square	R Square Adjusted
Y	0,153	0,137
Z	0,270	0,259

Source: Data Analysis, 2021

The Adjusted R Square value indicates that price, promotion, location, and facilities collectively contribute 13.7% to culinary tourism. The tourism marketing variable influences the price, promotions, locations, and facilities, resulting in an adjusted r Square value of 25.9%. Furthermore, various factors influence the remaining percentage of both.

7. Hypothesis Testing

The hypothesis test in PLS SEM can be conducted by comparing the t count value (to) with the t table value (tα).

Table 5. Statistic And p-values

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
X1 -> Y	0,039	0,041	0,018	2,155	0,032
X1 -> Z					
X2 -> Y	0,012	0,013	0,010	1,174	0,241
X2 -> Z					
X3 -> Y	0,028	0,029	0,013	2,073	0,039
X3 -> Z					
X4 -> Y	0,054	0,055	0,023	2,315	0,021
X4 -> Z					
Z -> Y					

Source: Data Analysis, 2021

The t-statistical value for the influence of affordable price on halal culinary tourism in the City of Medan, as indicated in Table 8, is 2.155. This value exceeds the critical t-value of 1.961, suggesting that there is a significant influence. Additionally, the original sample estimate value is 0.032. This indicates that the affordability of the price for the buyer does not have a substantial impact on the halal gastronomic tour in the city of Medan. In contrast to the findings of (Bulan and al, 2019), which indicated a notable impact of multiple factors such as price, promotions, location, and products on the inclination to revisit.

According to the data in table 8, the t-statistical value for the impact of Islamic promotion on halal culinary tourism in Kota Medan is 1.174, which is less than the critical t-value of 1.961. The original sample estimate value is 0.012. This demonstrates that Islamic promotions exert a substantial impact on halal gastronomic tourism in Kota Medan. Consistent with the findings of (Suparmin and Yusrizal, 2018), additional obstacles faced by the culinary industry involve effectively targeting non-Muslim consumers and catering to the preferences of the millennial demographic.

According to the data in Table 8, the t-statistical value for the impact of location on halal culinary tourism in Kota Medan is 2.073, which is greater than the critical t-value of 1.961. The original sample estimate value is 0.028. Therefore, it can be inferred that the location of Kota Medan does not have a significant impact on halal culinary tourism. As a result, the third hypothesis is rejected. Contrary to the aforementioned study, which asserts that factors such as knowledge, motivation, travel arrangements, accommodation, and availability of halal food and beverages have a substantial impact on the level of interest among Muslim tourists traveling halal in West Sumatra. The test results examining the impact of shariah-compliant facilities on halal culinary tourism in the city of Medan are presented in Table 8. The original sample estimate value obtained is 0.054, with a significance level above 10%. This is indicated by the t-statistical value of 2.315, which is greater than the critical t-table value of 1.961. The P value of 0.021 is less than 0.10, indicating that the application of non-Islamic influenced facilities has a significant impact. Therefore, it can be concluded that the fourth hypothesis is rejected. These findings contradict the study conducted by (Setiadi, 2018), which asserts that tourist facilities have a substantial impact on tourists' decisions to visit.

8. Impact of Price, Promotion, Location, and Restaurant Facilities on Halal Culinary Tourism in Medan with Intervening Tourism Marketing

The testing of the inner model (structural model) yielded an adjusted r-square value of 0.259 (25.9%) for tourism marketing. Based on these values, it can be inferred that this aligns with the teachings of An-Nisa 100 in the Qur'an, which emphasizes that Islam encourages various forms of travel such as hijrah, Hajj, pilgrimage, trade, and even tourism for the purpose of seeking knowledge. This aligns with the findings of a study conducted by (Kurniawan and Lismayasari, 2019), which revealed that the impact of promoting halal culinary products on the performance of small and medium-sized enterprises (UMKM) is mediated by digital marketing. Despite some variables having low values, digital marketing is shown to have a significant positive effect due to its high values.

9. Impact of Tourism Marketing on Halal Culinary Tourism in Field City Adjusted Square

The test yielded results of 0.137 (13.7%) and 86.3%, with the latter being influenced by unexamined factors. Additional factors mentioned in this case include seasonal influences, where the seasonal factor determines whether the number of tourist visits will increase or not, such as during school vacation season, Eid al-Adha, and Eid al-Fitr. During this season, there is likely to be a significant influx of tourists who travel to various regions or destinations to enjoy their vacation. Many of these tourists may specifically embark on a halal culinary tour. The Qur'an confirms that the tradition of the Quraysh is to travel to Yemen in the winter and to Sham in the summer. Furthermore, this aligns with the findings of a study conducted by (Liu and Dong, 2021), which demonstrates that knowledge management has the potential to enhance services by fostering sustainable marketing commitments.

10. Price, promotion, location, and restaurant facilities affect Medan's Halal culinary tourism.

According to the test results, with a P value of 0.032 being less than 0.10, it can be inferred that the first hypothesis is rejected. The price variables offered to tourists do not have a significant impact on halal culinary tourism in the City of Medan. According to a study conducted by (Kusuma and Sujana, 2021), price perception does not have a significant impact on rebuy interest among Nako Coffee consumers in Bogor City. The study also found that tourist interest in culinary tourism in the city of Malang is influenced by factors such as service, product quality, location, and price.

11. *Tourism Marketing Management in the City of Medan*

A study conducted by (Insasi, 2021) on small and medium-sized enterprises in the gastronomic industry in the Medan area revealed that numerous food products are being marketed beyond the town of Medan.

5 CONCLUSION

According to the mean AVE variance value for the six variables under investigation, convergence validity is satisfactory for all of them. Furthermore, the cross loading values for price question indicators (X1.3) are 0.798 points greater than those for the remaining construction indicators (X2 (0.042), X3 (0.199), X4 (0.132), Z (0.277), and Y (0.205), indicating strong discrimination validity. The reliability values of all components included in the study were satisfactory, as evidenced by a composite reliability test value of $0.70 > 0.60$.

Based on the outcomes of the outer weight test, it was determined that the price and promotion variables, in conjunction with the location and facility variables, exhibited a P-value below the significance level (0.05) and a T-count greater than 1.97. These results suggest that the variable under investigation possesses overall validity in this study. 13.7% of the adjusting square of halal culinary tourism was determined to be influenced by the price, promotion, location, and facility variables, according to the results of the r square and r adjusted square tests. In the meantime, the 25.9% r-adjustable square suggested that halal gastronomic tourism, along with price, promotions, location, and facilities, mediated the relationship between tourism marketing and the aforementioned variables. However, the remaining 74.1% was impacted by unexplored factors in the present study. The findings of the study indicate that neither location nor price have any discernible impact on halal culinary tourism in the city of Medan. Conversely, the facilities and promotional factors influence halal gastronomic tourism.

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REFERENCES

- Badan Pendapatan Daerah Kota Medan. 2021
- Badan Pusat Statistik. 2020. *Kota Medan Dalam Angka 2020*.
- Bahrul Setiadi. 2018. Pengaruh Harga, Lokasi Dan Fasilitas Wisata Terhadap Keputusan Berkunjung Wisatawan (Studi pada Objek Wisata Pantai Tiga Warna di Kabupaten Malang). *Jurnal Ilmiah Mahasiswa FEB*. Vol 6 (1).
- Chandra, T., Rakhmanto, A., Syamsudin, B., Marsongko, E. P., & Suhendar, T. 2023. Studi Analisis Pemasaran Wisata Kuliner Kota Yogyakarta. *Altasia Jurnal Pariwisata Indonesia*, 5(1), 55. <https://doi.org/10.37253/altasia.v5i1.7260>
- Chih-Hsing Sam Liu dan Tse-Ping Dong. 2021. *Discovering the relationship among knowledge management, sustainability marketing and service improvement: the moderating role of consumer interest*. *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*. Vo.33 (8).
- Cupian, Annisa Rahmadita dan Sarah Annisa Noven. 2021. Analisis Faktor-Faktor yang Mempengaruhi Minat Masyarakat Mengunjungi Wisata Halal Sumatra Barat (Studi

- Kasus Wisatawan Muslim Milenial Indonesia). *Jurnal Ilmiah Ekonomi Islam*, Vol.7(03).
- F. Insani. 2021. Analisis E-Commerce Sebagai Ekonomi Digital Dalam Mendorong Pertumbuhan Perekonomian Kota Medan Di Tengah Pandemi Covid-19 (Studi Kasus Pada Umkm Di Kota Medan). Skripsi. Universitas Islam Negeri Sumatera Utara.
- Hasibuan, V. Y., Yusrizal., Nurul Jannah. 2023. Analisa Pengembangan Wisata Kuliner Kota Medan. *Jurnal Ekonomi Bisnis Manajemen dan Akuntansi Universitas Labuhan Batu*. Vol.4 No.1, Juni 2023.
- Husein, A. S., 2015. Penelitian Bisnis dan Manajemen menggunakan Partial Least Squares (PLS) dengan smart PLS 3.0. Universitas Brawijaya.
- Kusuma, N. D., & Sujana, S. (2021). Pengaruh Kualitas Produk, Persepsi Harga, Dan Suasana Toko Terhadap Minat Beli Ulang Pada Konsumen Kopi Nako Di Kota Bogor. *Jurnal Ilmiah Pariwisata Kesatuan*, 2(2), 81–90. <https://doi.org/10.37641/jipkes.v2i2.784>
- P. Panca W, Jamin Ariana I, Arismayanti N. 2017. Pengaruh Kualitas Pelayanan Terhadap Loyalitas Wisatawan dan Citra Hotel Melati di Kelurahan Seminyak Kabupaten Badung Bali. *Jurnal Kepariwisata dan Hospitalis*, 1(1).
- Peraturan Daerah Provinsi Sumatera Utara Nomor 5 Tahun 2018 Tentang Rencana Induk Pembangunan Kepariwisata Provinsi Sumatera Utara Tahun 2017-2025
- Putu Hari Kurniawan dan Lismayasari. 2019. Wisata Kuliner Halal : Suatu Tinjauan Strategis Pemasaran Digital Terhadap Peningkatan Kinerja UMKM. *Jurnal Dinamika ekonomi dan Bisnis*. Vol.16. No.01. P: 1-11.
- Sarwono, Jonathan & Umi Narimawati. 2015. Membuat Skripsi, Tesis, dan Disetasi dengan Partial Least Square SEM (PLS-SEM). Yogyakarta: Penerbit ANDI.
- Siti Fatimah. 2019. Analisis Pengaruh Citra Destinasi Dan Lokasi Terhadap Minat Berkunjung Kembali. *Majalah Ilmiah Bahari Jogja (MIBJ)*. Vol. 17 No. 2. P : 27-40.
- Sudirman Suparmin dan Yusrizal. 2018. Strategi Pengembangan Pariwisata Halal. *Tansiq*, Vol. 1, No. 2
- Sugiyono. 2012. Memahami Penelitian Kualitatif. Bandung: Alfabeta
- Tengku Putri Lindung Bulan dan M. Lutfi Azmi. 2019. Pengaruh Strategi Bauran Pemasaran terhadap Minat Berkunjung Kembali di Objek Wisata Ruang Terbuka Hijau Taman Hutan Kota Langsa. *Jurnal Manajemen Dan Keuangan*. Vol. 8, No 3.
- Wahyu Ario Pratomo, et al. 2019. Pemetaan Restoran Halal di Pulau Samosir Sumatera. *Published by TALENTA Publisher Universitas Sumatera Utara Utara*. EE Conference Series 02.